

MULTILEVEL MARKETING IN FMCG

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INTRODUCTION

Multilevel marketing in FMCG means fast-moving consumer goods is possible through various platforms that we will discuss further. We all know about the marketing of the products because whenever a company makes a product and if they want to spread this news among the consumers, they first need to do good marketing of the products through various platforms like online platforms and offline platforms both. On online platforms, they can make a website of their company where they can list the products which they want to sell and can provide information about what is the price of the product and its guarantee period and how much discount is a company providing to the customer so that product can be well known to the knowledge of the consumers.

POPULAR FMCG COMPANIES

- Nestle
- Unilever
- P&G
- Pepsi
- Coca-Cola
- Johnson & Johnson
- Amway India

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FMCG generally includes various daily use products such as toothpaste, soap, shampoo, cosmetics, hair oil, detergents, LED bulbs, plastic goods, paper, and stationery products, and many more. Some more products like pharmaceuticals, chocolate, and soft drinks are also the products that FMCG companies serve.

MARKETING STRATEGY OF FMCG COMPANIES

FMCG companies always make marketing policies and good relationships with their customers by which they increase their profit. They always keep loyalty and awareness of their product by doing their survey to know the actual need of the customer. Companies utilize different marketing programs to promote their product in a wide range. FMCG products are the most sold products at a low cost and this is because of some strategies like companies put low shelf life of their products so that after some time customer will again buy the product. Coca-Cola, Unilever, and Nestle companies are the most popular companies in the FMCG sector because they know their customer's needs very deeply that's why they make their products accordingly.

BETTER TRANSPORTATION AND WAREHOUSING

Companies try to fulfill the demands of their customers by doing a survey and they also work upon good transport services and warehousing. By doing good care of their products, they can win the loyalty of the customers and next time customers will be more convenient buying stuff from them because its quality is good due to good transport services the product is not broken and defective and secondly by keeping things in good condition in the warehouse until they sale the product to the customers. Suppose some things need refrigeration then they keep that stuff in the right condition to avoid any kind of defect in the product.

COMBINATION OF PRICE, DISTRIBUTION & PROMOTION METHOD

Good FMCG companies always make a top-level strategy for the promotion of their products through different platforms like nowadays companies give their products to YouTube creators who are having 5 lacs or above subscribers on their channel when they advertise the product because subscribers are emotionally attached with them so there are high chances to believe on

products and to buy them and use them without any fear because their ideal people are also the products. By selling products at genuine prices, company can gain the faith of the

customer which can increase the profit and proper distribution of their products throughout the globe.

CONCLUSION

FMCG marketing strategies make the product selling much effective. Companies just need to focus on the different social platform for the promotion of their products because nowadays every single person is using the internet and they have their Email accounts on the internet so that we can also create a graphical analysis that how many people are liking the products and about their gender and age also so that it makes us wiser to know the demand of the products. The price of the goods also plays an important role so make sure that you are having a reasonable price for the product to get goodwill from the customers so that next time they will buy products automatically. Also, focus on the distribution of the goods whether it is proper or not and transportation services are good enough or not also make sure that products are keeping in good condition in the warehouse. All these important areas are well planned then only FMCG companies can earn well.

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